

The University of Eastern Piedmont is coordinating INJECTHEAL: a European project worth over 7 million euro for the treatment of chronic wounds

Novara 03 June 2025 – The **Università del Piemonte Orientale** announces the official start of **INJECTHEAL**, a research project dedicated to the development of new solutions for the treatment of chronic wounds, coordinated by Professor **Lia Rimondini**, head of the Department of Health Sciences.

INJECTHEAL was awarded a grant of about EUR 7.3 million under the Horizon Europe programme, with a total project cost of more than EUR 7.9 million. The planned duration of the project is three years, from 1 May 2025 to 30 April 2028.

Chronic wounds represent a significant clinical condition, affecting a large percentage of the population. These conditions can affect patients' quality of life and incur significant costs to healthcare systems. Current therapeutic strategies have limitations in treating deep wounds, controlling infection and inflammation, and supporting tissue regeneration.

At the heart of the project is the development of a 4D injectable hydrogel, designed for the targeted release of healing properties into complex wounds and to support tissue regeneration processes, contributing to the reduction of inflammatory and infectious processes. The hydrogel will be developed using sustainable materials, with the goal of providing an advanced therapeutic option, particularly for “deep tunnelling” wounds.

'The coordination of INJECTHEAL represents a significant commitment for our University in the field of transnational research' said Prof. Lia Rimondini. 'The aim of the project is to develop a therapeutic approach that can improve the management of chronic wounds. We will work in close collaboration with doctors and patients, with a focus on their opinions and needs. This will allow us to develop a solution that is really useful and easy to use in everyday practice'.

The consortium of INJECTHEAL consists of 13 partners from 8 European countries (Italy, Austria, Germany, Ireland, Spain, Switzerland, and the UK). This partnership includes academic institutions, research centres, small and medium-sized enterprises and industry organisations, united in the aim of contributing to the advancement of knowledge and applications in the field of chronic wound healing.

INJECTHEAL is funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101177924. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

INJECTHEAL

INJECTABLE GEL FOR CHRONIC WOUNDS

PROJECT FACTSHEET

INJECTHEAL	
Project title	Multifunctional Self-Healing Injectable Hydrogel for Chronic Wound Healing and Tissue Regeneration
Acronym	INJECTHEAL
Start date	01 May 2025
End date	30 April 2028
Total cost	7 944 558.03 €
EU Funding	7 299 588.80 €
Coordinator	Università del Piemonte Orientale

OUR PARTNERS

Universities:

- [Università del Piemonte Orientale](#) (UPO), Italy
- [Universität Siegen](#) (US), Germany
- [Trinity College Dublin](#) (TCD), Ireland
- [University of Brighton](#) (UoB), UK
- [Politecnico di Torino](#) (POLITO), Italy
- [Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana](#) (SUPSI), Switzerland

Research Centres:

- [Joanneum Research Forschungsgesellschaft MbH](#) (JR), Austria
- [Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas – INGENIO](#) (INGE), Spain

SMEs:

- [EU CORE Consulting](#) (EUCORE), Italy
- [Akribes Biomedical GmbH](#) (AKR), Austria
- [Tissue Click Ltd.](#) (TC), UK

Charities:

- [The Lindsay Leg Club Foundation](#) (LCF), UK

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